

Augmented Reality

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ABSTRACT

The term "augmented reality" refers to the merging of the physical environment with digital elements. Computer-generated visuals are superimposed upon the actual environment to accomplish this. There are four main categories of augmented reality: marker-based, marker-less, projection-based, and superimposition-based. It may be used for a wide variety of practical purposes. The medical, educational, industrial, robotic, and even the entertainment industries have all found uses for augmented reality. Mixed reality encompasses the realm of augmented reality. One way to look at it is as a mirror image of virtual reality. The origins of augmented reality are discussed in this study.

Keywords- Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality, Mixed Reality, Real world, Virtual world.

I. INTRODUCTION

The term "augmented reality" (AR) refers to a set of technologies that seamlessly merge digital elements with the physical environment. AR was formerly only seen in science fiction and academic circles. In the beginning, augmented reality systems were mostly used for experimentation and were tailored to accomplish certain goals, including fixing broken things. Recently, augmented reality (AR) has made its way out of the lab and into a broad variety of fields and industries, such as autonomous vehicles, marketing, education, entertainment, military, manufacturing, medical, smart cities, social media, and tourism. Its widespread use in industries as diverse as gaming, entertainment, advertising, and medicine has contributed to its rising profile.

It's no secret that augmented reality (AR) has been a hot issue in the world of software engineering for years, but with the arrival of innovative new hardware like Google Glass, AR is once again in the spotlight. A technology called augmented reality that uses the camera on your smartphone to superimpose digital information on top of real-world items, such as audio, video, and graphics. This is accomplished via the use of computer vision-based recognition algorithms. It's an effective method of rendering the world as it is and presenting it interactively, making virtual components seem like they belong in the actual one.

With augmented reality displays, you may enter a new universe in which the lines between the real and virtual are blurred. It isn't restricted to computers or mobile phones.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

[1]. Riya Aggarwal, "The impact of augmented reality on our lives" demonstrates how this technology may facilitate communication over great distances. The lack of robust security mechanisms in this technology is a drawback. MICROSOFT HOLOLENS is a piece of technology that combines augmented reality with virtual reality. HoloLens doesn't transport us to a fantastical other reality. By using HoloLens, we may remain in our current setting while having access to a wide range of digital features superimposed over our actual surroundings. With HoloLens, we may also engage with the augmented digital content. In sum, augmented reality technology is still in its early stages of development and is rapidly evolving. Recently, this technology has been used in the creation of several new items. After 5 years away, it has returned to the automotive repair industry. For the most part, despite numerous potential obstacles, the future of AR seems quite promising. [2]. J.T.Preethy, "A Sneak Peek at Augmented Reality as an Innovative Teaching Tool," This article will provide a summary of the most popular approach used when creating augmented reality apps. The emphasis of this study is on marker-based augmented reality, in which a user's smartphone scans a stationary 2D picture to reveal a 3D model, audio, video, or a mix of these. We may conclude that if more effort is put into studying the immersive quality of AR on mobile devices, users' future experiences may improve. As a cross-disciplinary idea, this technology has promising potential (AR). [3]. Zhenliang Zhang, "An AR View from the Other Side," A virtual agent, based on Minsky's description of the human mind, may grow its own conscious awareness and thrive with in virtual world just as people do in the real one. In this work, we present the idea of IAR and demonstrate that how virtual and real worlds are connected. When it comes to the online world, self-intelligence

is crucial. The orange avatar is the virtual assistant. Cons: expensive development costs and insufficient safety measures. We conclude that this approach considerably aids the development of an inverse augmented reality system by highlighting the potential role that self-intelligence might play in the virtual environment. We also demonstrate how the opposite of AR may be achieved with current technology by presenting an example implementation of an AR system. [4]. Zhongyang Zheng, "Aristo: Augmented Reality: A System for Full Participation" In this article, we describe Aristo, an augmented reality platform that use haptic feedback to enhance the experience of engaging with digital content. Using the Aristo framework, we have built up two working apps. Vivepaper, the first app, is a digital book that can be browsed and read in full immersion. The second option is a web-based tutorial meant to educate inexperienced employees. Vivepaper is used to demonstrate the platform's performance needs by demonstrating the many methods in which a user may see & listen to multimedia material with just their fingertips. ConsNo display protection unlike gorilla glass, and less possibility for cohesion. The vertical fields of education, training, & tourism all benefit from our deployment of Aristo like an augmented reality platform. In order to demonstrate our design choices and parameter settings for marker tracking & gesture detection, we will utilize Vivepaper, one of the platform's released apps, as an example.

III. COMPONENT USED

A computer, a screen, sensors, and controls are all necessary hardware aspects in augmented reality. Smartphones and tablets, as well as other modern mobile computing devices, often feature these components, which may be used as AR platforms thanks to the presence of a camera & MEMS sensors such an accelerometer, GPS, & solid state compass. Diffractive waveguides & reflecting waveguides are utilized in augmented reality.

A) Display

Optic projection systems, monitors, mobile devices, and display systems worn on the human body are only some of the technologies utilized in augmented reality rendering. One kind of wearable display is the head-mounted display (HMD), which may be attached to a harness or a helmet and worn on the front of the head. Head-mounted displays (HMDs) superimpose pictures of the real world and digital objects on the user's field of vision. In order to properly align virtual data with the actual environment and adapt to the user's head motions, many modern HMDs incorporate sensors for 6 levels of freedom monitoring. Head-mounted displays allow virtual reality users to move about and work together in a virtual environment..

B) Eyeglasses

The technology exists to create AR displays on glasses-like devices. The augmented reality (AR) picture is either transmitted via or bounced off surfaces of eyewear lens components in some systems, while in other versions, the eyewear itself uses cameras for intercepting actual view of the world and re-display its enhanced view via eyepieces.

C) HUD

An transparent display which provides information without distracting the user from their natural line of sight is called a head-up display (HUD). Heads-up displays, the forerunner of today's augmented reality headsets, were originally designed for pilots as in 1950s to save them from having to glance down so at instruments while in flight. Similar functionality can be provided by a head-up display, but practical applications of augmented reality are more likely include registration & tracking of the augmented perceptions, feelings, information, data, and pictures with at least some part of actual environment.

D) Contact lenses

Contact lenses with augmented reality displays are now in the works. Integrated electronics, light-emitting diodes (LEDs), and a wireless communication antenna might all be part of these bionic contact lenses' in-lens displays. Contact lens displays were originally recorded in 1999, and then again in 2010–2011, 11 years later. The U.S. military is also working on a pair of contact lenses that will work in tandem with augmented reality glasses, enabling troops to simultaneously concentrate on near-eye augmented reality pictures or far real world items.

E) Virtual retinal display

The Human Interface Technology Laboratory so at University of Washington, led by Dr. Thomas A. Furness III, is working to create a VRD (virtual retinal display) as a personal display device. Using this system, a display is scanned onto the viewer's retina. As a consequence, sharp, well-defined pictures with plenty of detail are produced. The screen looks to be a standard monitor, but it is really floating in the air.

F) Eye Tap

The Eye Tap, often called as Generation-2 Glass, intercepts natural light as it passes past pupil of wearer's eye and replaces it with artificial, computer-controlled light.

G) Handheld

Handheld displays utilize portable, tiny screens that may be handled with one hand. Today, video see-through is used by every portable augmented reality system. In the beginning, fiducial markers were used in portable AR devices, but later on, GPS units & MEMS sensors like digital compasses & 6 degrees of freedom gyroscope have been used. A first successful development for augmented reality technology may come from handheld displays. The mobility of handheld devices & pervasiveness of cameras in smartphones are 2 of key benefits of handheld augmented reality.

H) Spatial

Without the need for specialized displays like monitors, head-mounted displays, or hand-held devices, SAR enhances real-world objects and settings. In SAR, digital projectors are used to superimpose visual data onto real-world objects. When using SAR, the display is physically isolated from the consumers. Since SAR's displays aren't tied to specific users, it's easy to employ with large groups of people in a physical space.

I) Tracking

Digital cameras or other image devices, gyroscopes, global positioning systems, accelerometers, solid-state compasses, and Radio-frequency identification are only some of the motion tracking technologies used in today's mobile augmented-reality systems (RFID). Each of these technologies comes with its own degree of precision and accuracy. What matters most is the user's head position and orientation. One way to achieve 6DOF interaction is by tracking the user's hands or a portable input device.

J) Networking:

The widespread usage of mobile and, in particular, wearable devices has led to the rise in popularity of augmented reality apps on mobile platforms. They often depend, however, on computationally demanding computer vision having stringent latency constraints. Data processing is sometimes requested to be offloaded to a remote computer that make up for lack of computing capability. Offloading computations imposes additional limits on programs, most particularly in the case of latency and throughput.

K) Input devices:

Methods include voice recognition systems, which convert user speech into computer commands, and gesture recognition systems, which decode human motion by visual detection or sensors in a wand, pen, pointer, glove, or other wearable. Wave by Seebright Inc. & Nimble by Intugine Technologies are two products aiming to control augmented reality goggles.

IV. ARCHITECTURE

The basic premise of augmented reality is that we may supplement our perception of the actual world around us with computer-generated sensory input by using a technology gadget. Fig. 1 depicts the recommended technique.

Figure 1: Architecture Of Augmented Reality

A. Creation of 3D Models

Step one in 3D modeling is collecting data in the form of spatial coordinates and orientations for the item in question. Due to the characteristics of image-based modelling techniques, items with plain, clear, glossy, or reflecting surfaces will not operate properly. The usage of either underexposed or overexposed pictures causes the same issues. Multiple shots will be taken by taking at least a looping of consecutive photographs around the subject. When taking shots, it is best to keep the subject stationary and utilize a same light levels throughout.

Additionally, to aid 3D reconstruction, is also advised that the item being shot fills at minimum 70% of pixels in the photographs and that the series of images does have some overlap. The collection of pictures can now be analyzed through an image-based modelling framework. We utilized Autodesk Memento Beta, a tool for transforming recorded reality data into editable, high-resolution models, to write this article. It's possible that further polishing is needed to get rid of extraneous noise or cluttered backgrounds in the final 3D model.

Autodesk Memento's intelligent selection & clean up features allow for quick and easy repair & tidying up. Once Autodesk Memento has finished reconstructing the 3D model, it may be exported in a number of different formats (including OBJ, STL, PLY, and FBX) complete with textures. It is recommended by Aumentaty that models be exported to FBX for processing since this format is one of the ones recognized with our AR creation tool.

B. Creation of AR

Content With Aumentaty Author, creating an augmented reality interactive element is a visible and straightforward procedure. To begin seeing the scene dynamically while it's being built, a marker is chosen from marker ID menu & printed. The next step is to turn on the camera and direct it toward the printed marker. When the marker is being processed by the AR program, it will become orange on the computer screen. From here, the user may locate the model they created in the previous phase & drag it to the models library section of interface to icon representing the marker they printed during the initial step. In the software's user interface, the 3D model will be superimposed over the marker to provide as a visual indication of the connection. The FBX, DAE, & OBJ file formats are all supported by the software for loading 3D models.

If you're going to be using textures, they need to be part of 3D file. Whenever a scene is exported and viewed in Aumentaty Viewer, any animations included in the model will be automatically played indefinitely. The 3D may be repositioned, scaled, and rotated in reference to marker using the main panel's controls. This enables fundamental scene modifications, which are helpful in several scenarios, like when model's vertical orientation differs from the scene of the marker or when the 3D model is excessively big in comparison to the marker. This fundamental procedure will be carried out as many times as there are models and markers in the program. The maximum number of models that may be in a scenario is 12.

At last, the whole augmented reality environment, including all markers and models, will be transferred to Aumentaty Viewer for viewing on any camera-enabled device (desktop or mobile). The augmented reality sceneries made in Aumentaty Author may be seen in Aumentaty Viewer, a 3D content viewer. Information may be sent to mobile devices, emailed, or posted on social media. Fig. 2 is an illustration of the procedure.

Figure 2: AR creation process: (a) real object, (b) reconstructed mesh (low quality), (c) cleaned textured model, (d) augmented reality content

Creators of augmented reality content may skip the scripting and programming using Aumentaty Author's graphical environment and instead get a feel for the medium as it takes shape. Authoring tool use and marker interaction become second nature to users fairly quickly. Although the suggested technique is straightforward, it still requires users to have physical access to the item being modeled, that could be difficult depending on the topic at hand. Reconstructing the 3D model requires a lot of computing power, thus time is also an essential component.

V. APPLICATIONS

5.1GOOGLE GLASS

The introduction of Google Glass in 2013 (fig. 3) is often seen as the moment at which augmented reality first attracted widespread media attention. Google Glass sparked a renewed interest in augmented reality among certain businesses and techies, despite skepticism from the general public. Since then, major tech companies have spent a lot of time and money expanding and improving augmented reality technology.

Figure 3: First Developed Augmented Reality Device

Using Wi-Fi, the gadget will likely share information with users' mobile phones, play videos in response to their requests, and recognize their voices. Google produced a short film highlighting the functionality of Google Glass and its many applications. Communication, navigation, & social networking are its primary focuses. The camera can detect its surroundings and identify the people and things in them. The functionality of Google Glass is entirely dependent on the user's vocal commands..

5.2 AR ON SMARTPHONE

New developments in augmented reality algorithms have propelled augmented reality on mobile devices to new heights. It's a novel Augmented Reality-based technology that can be used on a variety of handheld gadgets, including smartphones, tablets, game consoles, and military HUDs. It improves and elongates mobile device's functionality & utility.

Figure 4 : Augmented Reality In Smart Phone

Augmented reality may be used in the mobile context through the device's camera, its location services, or both. On the screen, the spectator can watch the camera's input being altered.

As the size and quality of mobile devices' displays, CPU speeds, cameras, and battery life all increase, augmented reality's popularity rises. Expanding game options include augmented reality titles featuring cats, dragons, and legos. The use of augmented reality (AR) has progressed beyond its novelty to the realm of serious learning.

5.3 GOOGLE'S NEW STAR WAR AR STICKERS

The release of "AR Stickers" app marks a major step forward in Google's efforts to popularize Augmented Reality (fig 5). While Google's Project Tango devices have been capable of augmented reality for such time now, AR Sticker is first app under Google's new augmented reality strategy that centers on ARCore. ARCore is an updated augmented reality platform that does a lot of tricks as Tango AR, but without the need for any additional hardware.

These adorable 3D stickers are compatible with Google's camera app and use the latest augmented reality (AR) technology to magically appear in your photographs and videos as if they were part of the original shot. Unfortunately, you can only get these augmented reality stickers on a Pixel phone for now. They also need an Android 8.1 upgrade, which isn't available for all phones just yet. Those who have upgraded to Android 8.1 may expect to see the new function in the camera app in the "coming days," according to Google. It also has future intentions to produce more sticker packs.

Fig5: Google's New Star War Ar Stickers

5.4 AUGMENTED REALITY IN MILITARY

The use of augmented reality isn't always a joke. For use in warfare, US Army is testing out augmented reality applications that will improve the ability of soldiers to identify friendly from enemy forces (fig 6).

The military has a long history of being an early adopter of new technologies, particularly for the improvement of training and weaponry. Armies must adapt to the ever-changing nature of battle by monitoring emerging military "trends" and seeking technical advantages. Moreover, the number of AR applications in the military is growing at an exponential rate as new data & graphics processing capabilities become available.

Fig6 : Augmented Reality In Military

The tactical augmented reality (TAR) glasses resemble NVG, but they have much more potential. A soldier may use it to see where they are in relation to friendly & hostile troops. By displaying relevant information directly in front of soldier's eyes, TAR heads-up display may increase situational awareness, reduce weight of equipment, & aid in defeating enemy more effectively.

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

The potential applications of augmented reality technology extend well beyond the realm of entertainment. Some experts predict that the healthcare sector will produce roughly \$5 billion in income by 2025, and that this sector would benefit most from augmented reality technology. With 84% of customers across the globe believing AR is potential of tourism, the sector is poised for growth. Whenever it comes to increasing the speed with which a job may be completed or quality of experience that the user is left with, augmented reality (AR) is the technology of the future.

While augmented reality technology is still in its infancy, it is already assisting medical professionals in making life-saving diagnoses and choices. These innovations may help reduce the total cost of medical treatment.

VII. CONCLUSION

A quick overview of AR has been provided. It provides an explanation of what Augmented Reality (AR) is, along with its benefits and drawbacks. It lays down the fundamental structure needed to create an AR app from scratch. We also talk about the many uses for AR right now, including in the gaming, medical, military, and marketing industries. We have gathered the various AR app development environments currently accessible.

As we go farther into the digital era, augmented reality promises to transform our surroundings in real time via our smartphones, glasses, automobile windshields, and even windows. Augmented reality privacy concerns are significant. By augmenting our senses of sight, sound, touch, and smell, augmented reality (AR) technology would only further obscure boundary between what is genuine what is computer created.

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